

Improving housing affordability through housing allowances: a pilot project in Croatia

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1. Introduction

Housing affordability is one of the most pressing social problems in most EU Member States. Cities, especially capital cities, are experiencing a significant influx of inhabitants, leading to an increase in housing costs. This gradual densification process combined with slow housing construction is exacerbating affordability inequality for average earners, with the gap widening for those on below average incomes, leaving more European households unable to afford adequate housing.

The inability of younger generations and the precariously employed to buy their own home is forcing them into the rental market, earning them the label "Generation Rent". The phenomena of financialisation and privatisation, particularly in CEE countries, have contributed to the high proportion of homeowners in societies. This worsens housing affordability since many housing units are converted into short-term rental properties, limiting long-term rental options and driving up rental prices. In urban centres, especially in capital cities, there is often a shortage of affordable housing options such as public or rental housing.

In this paper we will look at housing allowances, a special type of demand-side intervention that has characteristics of both a housing subsidy and an income subsidy. We will evaluate a Croatian pilot project in which housing allowances are distributed as a measure to increase housing affordability. Finally, we will recommend policy measures that should be considered for a greater impact of the housing allowances in Croatia.

2. Research method and aim

This paper aims to explain housing allowances from the Croatian perspective and assess whether this recent nationwide pilot project is a viable large-scale replicable solution to housing inequality and affordability. The research question underlying this paper is whether housing allowances can be used to increase housing affordability in the short term.

To this end, the research will be conducted in three steps. Firstly, a literature review will help us to understand the possible expectations of housing allowances as a demand-side subsidy and the impact on the quality of life of recipients as well as on the housing market in general. Secondly, interviews will be conducted with the relevant Croatian authorities to find out whether the aim of this pilot project has been achieved and whether housing allowance programmes may be introduced on a larger scale in the future. Thirdly, a questionnaire will be distributed to subsidy recipients to assess the real effect of this measure on their housing affordability and quality of life.

The expected outcome of this research is an overview of the housing allowance system in Croatian context and an understanding of the future scaling up potential.

3. Housing in Croatia

3.1 Housing since the independence

Croatia was under socialism until the early 1990s, when the socialist one-party system was replaced by democratic party pluralism. One of the most important measures that characterised the current housing regime was the process of “give-away” privatisation to sitting tenants and the privileged individuals from the socialist era, as well as the withdrawal of the state from the housing market. In the newly adopted constitution, the right to housing was not enshrined as a human right and the state's responsibility to provide housing for those in need was not mentioned. Furthermore, the newly formed government did not set up a national housing fund to oversee privatisation and reinvest the proceeds. Instead, privatisation was left to local authorities who had no knowledge, capacity or responsibility to carry out such an operation. This led to a transfer of publicly owned flats to individuals who had the means to acquire them for a fraction of the real market value. In addition to these “internal” forces that set in motion this path-dependent development of housing policy and institutions, which have not changed significantly to this day, Croatia faced an external pressure, namely the War of Independence, which devastated both human lives and the housing stock. The upshot of policy modernisation is a lack of institutional and political capacity to respond to the inflated housing market and the inability to implement an efficient housing policy.

In recent years, Croatia has faced different housing market challenges ranging from the global financial crisis, failure to produce a national housing strategy, low investment in social and public rental housing, the Swiss Franc crisis, COVID-19 crisis and its entrance into the Eurozone. In practically all these periods, housing was left to the market that mostly incentivised homeownership, thus worsening the housing market situation. Incentivising homeownership, if not followed by an increase in new construction and if the equal programmes are not provided to tenants, leads to widening the social inequalities and dividing households to “outsiders” and “insiders”.

Common “issues” with unaffordable housing is evident in young people either leaving Croatia and searching for better employment elsewhere or leaving home later in their lives and starting families, which has a dual effect: first the overcrowding rate increase due to more people living under the same roof, and second, a negative demographic trend. This is especially evident in Croatia with 44,4 percent overcrowding rate in young population between 16 and 29 (Figure 1), and the negative demographic balance between 2011 and 2021 census of nearly 10 percent¹ (Croatian Bureau of Statistics, 2023).

¹ Population in 2021 census was 3.871.833 compared to 4.284.889 in 2011

Figure 1. Overcrowding rate across EU Member States for age between 16 and 29, in 2022. Source: author, based on Eurostat (2023)

3.2 Current housing market

Housing affordability in Croatia is not absolute but relevant and it concerns both tenants and homeowners. While housing may be deemed unaffordable in large cities, such as the city of Zagreb, it may be more affordable in the area of 50 kilometres distance from the city centre.

Croatia has a specific housing market fragmentation, in which the housing market is mostly active in the city of Zagreb and on the Adriatic Sea coast, whereas other parts of Croatia have underdeveloped housing markets. Figures 2 and 3 below show the number of real estate transactions and the average (median) prices according to Croatian regions in 2022, respectively (Institute of Economics in Zagreb [EIZ] & Croatian Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets [MPGI], 2023). Figure 2 clearly indicates (in dark blue) which parts of Croatia were most sought after, and this is due to mostly investments for touristic purposes, not for living. This statement is also backed by the fact that Croatia among the leading countries in the EU in housing stock indicator with 604 dwellings per 1.000 inhabitants (Deloitte, 2022).

Figure 2. Number of transaction of apartments and houses in Croatian municipalities in 2022, Source: EIZ & MPGI (2023)

Figure 3. Median realised price of apartments and houses (in €) in Croatian municipalities in 2022, Source: EIZ & MPGI (2023)

Given this information, we conclude that there is a high pressure on housing prices in Zagreb and coastal cities, while the Eastern part of Croatia has much lower demand for housing and thus less pressure on housing affordability. However, we also know that around 90% of households own their homes. For them, paying utility bills and finding paid work are more important issues. Coupled with the fact that Croatia is an increasingly aging society, especially in rural areas where most of population are elderly pensioners homeowners are asset rich but cash poor², they are increasingly entering into risk of poverty.

4. Housing allowances

Social policies targeting affordable housing typically comprises three primary components: offering housing allowances to families facing housing-related financial difficulties, enhancing the social rented sector, and aiding low-income households within the owner-occupied sector (Bežovan, 2013; Hegedüs, 2007).

Demand side subsidies, such as housing allowances, allow recipients to procure or rent a residential unit in the housing market, while supply side, such as public or social rental housing do not (Coldburn, 2019). While supply side subsidies mostly subsidise “brick and mortar” such as social rental housing, demand side subsidies target people and households in need. There are cases where supply and demand side subsidies are combined. For instance, in Slovenia, residents in social rental housing are eligible for housing allowance of up to 80 percent of the rent.

² Since they own their home but have low monthly incomes to cover housing costs such as maintenance and utility bills

Housing allowance is both an income subsidy and housing subsidy, and in most cases, they are tenure neutral. Since housing allowance both serves to increase disposable income after housing costs are paid, it is part of social policy, but since it also increases housing consumption, it is part of housing policy (Bežovan, 2010). Thus, housing allowances are a hybrid instrument, and in practice the responsible authority is often either the Ministry of Social Security and Welfare or the Ministry of Housing.

Income subsidies can be “tied” or “untied” to a consumption item. Housing allowance is in this case “tied” and must be spent on housing. The formula for calculating housing allowances is called the “housing benefit gap” and is the difference between housing costs and household income spent on housing (Haffner & Boelhouwer, 2006). The impact of housing allowances on households’ disposable incomes can be significant and can fulfil an important function in income support. It distinguishes between the affordability of adequate housing and a sufficient budget available for expenses other than housing. The growing need for income support through housing allowances arises from new social risks, including single parenthood, precarious employment, long-term unemployment, mental health problems and working poverty. Housing allowance provides income support in times of temporary and long-term poverty (Griggs & Kemp, 2012).

Housing allowances are integral to welfare and housing policies, aiming to improve housing affordability and provide income support to individuals and households. However, their effect on rent levels is debated, varying across countries and contexts (Eerola & Lyytikäinen, 2021; Eriksen & Ross, 2015; Hyslop & Rea, 2019; Susin, 2002). The impact of housing allowances on rising rents remains uncertain, with studies suggesting conflicting results. Additionally, their influence on house prices differs across countries and time periods, presenting a complex issue (Eerola & Lyytikäinen, 2021; Hyslop & Rea, 2019).

4.1 Housing allowances in Croatia

In Croatia, there are currently several housing allowance support schemes, mostly reserved for low-income households. These include the housing allowance, fuel allowance, allowance for energy-challenged buyers at risk, and personal needs allowance for residential care beneficiaries. To qualify for the housing allowance, recipients must meet the criteria for the minimum guaranteed benefit, which ranges from €92.91 to €172.54 per month for single households, depending on various factors. The housing allowance covers rent, energy and utility bills, and renovation costs for energy efficiency enhancements. Local authorities administer these allowances, with heating allowances also available, providing firewood for those using such heating methods, and are disbursed annually (Government of Croatia, 2023).

Additionally, a national programme subsidises rent for full-time students in specific cities, including Pula, Rijeka, Varaždin, Split, and Zagreb. Under this program, 2,206 students receive €248.86 each (Central Office for Demography and Youth, 2023). However, this programme will not be the focus of this research.

4.2 Housing allowances pilot project

Since the beginning of 2023, there has been a national pilot programme that grants housing benefits to young individuals (under 30) and families (with recipients under 45) who rent in the private market and whose salary is not higher than the average national salary. The maximum monthly allowance is €180 for families (€2,160 annually) and €120 for individuals

and families without children (€1,440 annually) until 2023. These funds are allocated by the national government and distributed through local authorities, with each authority able to support up to 10 beneficiaries per year (Central Office for Demography and Youth, 2023a). The total budget for this pilot project amounts to €785,719.03.

The distribution of the housing allowance was carried out until the end of 2023 and the aim of this paper is to gather insights about this pilot project from two sides: from the government agency and from the beneficiaries.

5. Conclusion

Housing allowances need to reflect local housing needs, especially in Croatia, where property supply and prices vary significantly across regions. Coastal areas and Zagreb properties are highly sought after compared to rural areas and other cities, necessitating tailored approaches to adjust allowances based on living standards. With limited options for homeownership and inadequate social and rental housing, extending housing allowances to a wider population could alleviate short-term affordability issues until more public rental units are available. To combat the trend of young Croatians leaving the country due to housing challenges, modernising housing allowances to enhance affordability is imperative (Bežovan & Jakovčević, 2023).

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References

- Bežovan, G. (2010). Analiza sustava subvencioniranja najamnina i troškova stanovanja te prakse gradnje socijalnih stanova u Hrvatskoj [Analysis of the rent subsidy system and housing costs, and the practice of building social housing in Croatia], *Hrvatska i komparativna javna uprava: časopis za teoriju i praksu javne uprave*, 10(3).
- Bežovan, G. (2013). The Social Housing Search Delayed by Postwar Reconstruction. In J. Hegedüs, M. Lux, & N. Teller (Eds.), *Social Housing in Transition Countries* (pp. 128- 146). London: Routledge.
- Bežovan, G. & Jakovčević, D. (2023). Učinci stambenog zbrinjavanja mlađe populacije na demografske trendove u Zagrebu. [The effects of providing housing for the younger population on demographic trends in Zagreb.], *Revija za socijalnu politiku*, 30 (1), 1-21
<https://doi.org/10.3935/rsp.v30i1.1800>
- Central office for demography and young. (2023). *Pilot project public call- local self- government units for financial support aimed at co-financing costs housing for young families and young people in 2023.*
<https://demografijaimladi.gov.hr/UserDocsImages//Dokumenti//PILOTP~1.PDF>
- Central office for demography and young. (2023a). Notice on subsidizing housing costs for full-time students.
<https://demografijaimladi.gov.hr/vijesti-4693/obavijest-o-subvenciji-troskova-stanovanja-redovitim-studentima/6698>

- Croatian Bureau of Statistics. (2022). *The final results of the Census 2021 have been published*. <https://dzs.gov.hr/vijesti/objavljeni-konacni-rezultati-popisa-2021/1270>
- Coldburn, G. (2019). The use of markets in housing policy: a comparative analysis of housing subsidy programs. *Housing Studies* 36(1):1-34
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02673037.2019.1686129>
- Deloitte (2022, August). *Property Index - Overview of European Residential Markets*. 11th edition.
- Eerola, E., & Lyytikäinen, T. (2021). Housing Allowance and Rents: Evidence from a Stepwise Subsidy Scheme. *Scandinavian Journal of Economics*, 123(1), 84–109. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sjoe.12396>
- Eurostat. (2023). *Glossary: Housing cost overburden rate*. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Housing_cost_overburden_rate&lang=en
- Government of Croatia (2023). Zajamčena minimalna naknada. <https://gov.hr/hr/zajamcena-minimalna-naknada/714>
- Griggs, J., & Kemp, P. (2012). Housing allowances as income support: Comparing European welfare regimes. *International Journal of Housing Policy*, 12(4), 391–412. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616718.2012.711987>
- Haffner, M. E. A., & Boelhouwer, J. (2006). Housing allowances and economic efficiency. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 30(4), 944–959. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2427.2006.00699.x>
- Hegedüs, J., (2007). *Social Housing in Transition Countries. Social Housing in Europe*. London: LSE.
- Hyslop, D. R., & Rea, D. (2019). Do housing allowances increase rents? Evidence from a discrete policy change. *Journal of Housing Economics*, 46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhe.2019.101657>
- Institute of Economics in Zagreb & Croatian Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets (2023). Pregled tržišta nekretnina Republike Hrvatske [en. *Overview of the real estate market in the Republic of Croatia*], *Institute of Economics in Zagreb*.
- Susin, S. (2002). Rent vouchers and the price of low-income housing. *Journal of Public Economics*, 83, 109–152.